

**ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURAL TRAITS AND THE PERFORMANCE OF
ORGANIZATIONS IN BENIN CITY**

Ofuokwu, Faith O

Ovini Pogoson O

Department of Business Administration,
Auchi Polytechnic, Auchi, Edo State, Nigeria
Taraba State University, Jalingo

** Corresponding author: everestinox @yahoo.com

Abstract

This study examined the relationship between organizational cultural traits on performance of business organizations focusing on four commercial banks in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. In examining the relationship between organizational culture and performance of business organizations in Benin City, culture components such as sense of mission in the organization, consistency of organization culture, organizational adaptability, and employee involvement were correlated with performance components such as organization growth, employee's commitment, goal achievement and customers' satisfaction. The study used data collected from the research questionnaires and the data were analyzed using percentage and Pearson's product moment correlation analysis. The result revealed that the sense of mission in the organization, consistency in organization culture and organizational adaptability were found to have positive and significant relationship with organizational performance, while employee's involvement in the organization has no significant relationship with organizational performance. It was recommended that there should be training programmes for managers and employees on how to improve organization's product / service delivery to boost customer's satisfaction..

Keywords: Organisational Culture, Mission Traits, Consistency Traits, Adaptability Traits, And Involvement Traits
